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A Tendency of Work Life Balance in Flexible Work Arrangement-Overview

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Abstract— Organizations are under constant pressure to produce goods and services, of the right quality and at the right price, as and when customers want them. To meet these demands sometimes new ways of working have to be found to make the best use of staff and resources. Flexible patterns of work can help to address these pressures by maximizing the available labour and improving customer service. The need for "qualified flexible work arrangement" is increasing, both in India and globally. However, there have been major researches in India on the family factors that influence the amount or type of flexibility needed to support families in different circumstances, or on the impacts that the use of flexible work arrangements can have on family life. This article is based on the new tendency and models related with flexible working models. The study also found that many people choose their work to fit around family responsibilities. This article provides a summary of the research, with a focus on the findings that relate to the impact of flexible work on family life.

Keywords--- Tendency, Flexible Work Arrangement

I. INTRODUCTION

FLEXIBLE working describes any type of working arrangement that gives some degree of flexibility on how long, where and when employees work. While the statutory right to request flexible working may have helped make flexible working a familiar phrase within workplaces, flexible working arrangements has been an option in many employment sectors for a long time, helping employers meet the changing needs of their customers and their staff:

- Customers expect to have goods and services available outside of the traditional 9-5 working hours
- Employees want to achieve a better balance between work and home life
- Organizations want to meet their customers and employees needs in a way that enables them to be

as productive as possible

As employers, organizations also have a 'duty of care' to protect their employees from risks to their health and safety. These risks might include stress caused by working long hours or struggling to balance work and home life. Flexible working can help to improve the health and well-being of employees and, by extension, reduce absenteeism, increase productivity, and enhance employee engagement and loyalty.

Flexible working arrangements are already used in many different employment sectors, such as:

- Part-time work, often used in hotels, restaurants, shops, warehouses etc
- Flextime, mostly used in office based environments for staff below managerial level in public and private sector service organizations
- Annualized hours, often used in manufacturing and agriculture where there can be big variations in demand throughout the year. With developments in technology, particularly in the availability of communication tools (such as fast home broadband and smart phones), more and more roles could be compatible with some forms of flexible working arrangement. While there is never a guarantee that flexible working arrangements will have a considerable positive impact, if proper consideration is given to what options may be suitable, benefits can include:
 - A more efficient and productive organization
 - A more motivated workforce
 - Better retention of valuable employees
 - A wider pool of applicants can be attracted for vacancies
 - reduced levels of absence, sickness and stress
 - Better customer service and increased customer loyalty
 - Working hours that best suit the organization, its employees and its customers

II. CONSIDERING FLEXIBLE WORKING PRACTICES

A. Potential barriers to establishing flexible working practices

With any prospective change to working practices there are issues that need to be considered before action is

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taken. The concerns that employers may have implementing flexible working practices are:

- potential operational difficulties in making the proposed changes
- possible additional pressure placed on other workers who aren't requesting flexible working
- potential negative impact on customer service and quality of work
- resistance from managers
- difficulties in scheduling work with various work arrangements to consider
- additional costs
- potential difficulties in communicating with employees (e.g. homeworkers not being in the office)
- potential reduction in overall employee flexibility

While these barriers may mean that it is not possible or not appropriate to make the changes originally proposed, with due consideration, there are often ways to resolve the issues faced. An employer may also decide that some of the barriers cannot be resolved but are worth dealing with to reap the benefits that the flexible working change could bring.

A CIPD report on 'Flexible working provision and uptake' in 2012 found that 72% of the employers surveyed believed that implementing flexible working practices had a positive impact on staff engagement and 73% felt that it had a positive impact on employee motivation.

B. The importance of work-life balance

In today's society it is common for employees to have many competing responsibilities in their life. Examples of responsibilities away from work might include:

- care commitments involving children or elderly relatives
- Education commitments that limit availability at times of the week/month/year
- Duties and/or interests outside of work
- needing to be available for religious observances
- People wanting a greater sense of well being and reduced stress levels

A poor balance between an employee's work commitments and their other responsibilities can lead to stress, high absence and low productivity.

Employees who have a better work-life balance often have a greater sense of responsibility, ownership and control of their working life. If an employer helps an employee to balance their work and home life this can be rewarded by increased loyalty and commitment. They may also feel more able to focus on their work and to develop their career.

C. Flexible work arrangement atmosphere

Not all flexible working arrangements will be suitable in all work places. However, modern technology does mean that, with due consideration, most roles could accommodate some sort of flexible working arrangement. For example, options for frontline customer facing roles can be limited but flexitime, part-time working and job sharing could still be considered.

It is important that careful thought is given about the suitability of different forms of flexible working in the organization. **For example...**

An employer may be thinking about introducing annualized hours in order to increase production levels to meet infrequent rises in demand because they can work well where:

- There are peaks and troughs in work
- The workforce is required to be available with little notice

Alternatively the employer could decide to meet these increases in demand by introducing overtime because:

- it provides flexibility to meet fluctuations
- it would be a smaller change to the organization than annualized

8am to 10am	Flexible start time
10am to midday	Core time
Midday to 2pm	Flexible lunch period
2pm to 4pm	Core time
4pm to 6pm	Flexible finish time

The employer will need to decide what hours the working day includes, whether core time (where employees must work) is necessary and what happens at lunch breaks e.g. the possible start/finish times and the maximum/minimum lunch period that can be taken.

Hours of attendance should be recorded and added up at the end of each accounting period. Within limits, employees can carry over any excess or deficit in the number of hours they are required to work (typically between a day and a day-and-a-half per month). Some schemes can allow employees to take excess hours as additional leave, known as flexi-leave.

D. Part-time work

Part-time work is the most common type of flexible working. Part time working covers any arrangement where the employee is contracted to work anything less than typical full time hours for the type of work in question. Part time workers must not be treated less favourably than a full time worker doing the same or similar work.

E. Overtime

Overtime is normally hours that are worked over the usual full time hours; it can be compulsory or voluntary. A recognized system of paid overtime is more common with hourly paid staff than salaried staff.

There is no legal right to be paid a higher rate for any overtime worked. However, certain sectors, to encourage their employees to work overtime, do offer an improved overtime rate. For example, additional hours worked on some days of the week would carry payment at the normal rate, but hours on days that are less popular might carry a higher rate, such as time plus a quarter, time plus a half or even double time. What the employee would receive should be made clear in advance of any overtime being worked. It is important to remember when considering the cost and return associated with overtime, that employers are required to include some types of overtime payments when they calculate holiday pay.

F. Job sharing

Job sharing is a form of part-time working where two (or more) people share the responsibility for a full-time job. They share the pay and benefits in proportion to the hours each works. Job sharers may work split days, split weeks or alternate weeks.

G. Compressed hours

This is where an employee works their usual hours in fewer and/or longer blocks during the week. Through starting early and/or finishing late, employees can build up additional hours which they take as a day or half-day away from work.

For example... Compressed hours	
A typical 40 hour working week	9am to 5pm from Monday to Friday
A possible compressed 40 hour working week	9am to 6pm from Monday to Thursday 9am to 1pm on Friday
A possible compressed working fortnight (based on an average 40 hour working week)	9am-6pm on 9 of the 10 working days No working hours on 1 of the 10 working days

H. Shift work

Shift work is a pattern of work in which one employee replaces another doing the same job within a 24-hour period. Shift workers normally work in crews, which are groups of workers who make up a separate shift team. In some shift systems, each crew will regularly change its

hours of work and rotate morning, afternoon, and night shifts.

Continuous shift systems provide cover for 24 hours, seven days a week. Non-continuous shift systems provide cover for less than the total hours available in a week – for example five 24-hour periods in seven days or 12-hours out of the 24.

The Health and Safety Executive (HSE) has produced a risk index for shift working, which helps employers to analyse the link between shift patterns and employee fatigue. The risk index and other related information can be found in the human factors section at www.hse.gov.uk

I. Annualized hours

An annualized hour's system is where the total number of hours to be worked over the year is fixed but there is flexibility over the employee's daily and weekly working patterns. Typically, the times an employee is contracted to work are split into:

- Set shifts which cover the majority of the year
- Unallocated shifts which the employee can be asked to work at short notice

In some systems the employee is paid for unallocated shifts and 'owes' the time to the company. The company holds these hours or 'payback' shifts in reserve and can ask employees to work them at short notice, to cover for colleagues or to cope with a peak in demand

J. Calculating annualized hours

Methods can vary but a typical formula is:

1. The number of weeks per year
2. Less any annual leave entitlement
3. Multiplied by the number of working hours per week.

For example...

Based on a 40-hour working week and the statutory entitlement to 5.6 weeks annual leave per year:

1. Length of year is 52 weeks
2. Less annual leave of 5.6 weeks, making 46.4 weeks
3. Multiplied by 40 working hours per week
 46.4×40 hours per week = 1856 annual hours

K. Term-time working

Term-time working gives employees the opportunity to reduce their hours or take time off, usually unpaid, during any school holidays. An employer could also offer a similar arrangement to individuals in full time education e.g. university students, who are only able to work during the school holiday periods.

Salary can be paid either in 12 equal monthly installments or the employee could be paid for time worked and when annual leave is actually taken.

L. Temporary working and Fixed-term contracts

A temporary worker is someone employed for a limited period and whose job is usually expected by both sides to last for only a short time. Temporary workers may be employed directly by the employer or by private agencies. Agencies will recruit, select and sometimes train temporary workers and hire them out to employers

Temporary workers are sometimes hired on fixed-term contracts. A fixed-term contract is a contract of employment based on a definite period or the completion of a specific task or event. Employment ends when the contract expires.

Fixed-term contracts should contain a period of notice for early termination. This means that if circumstances change the contract can be ended by either party before the expiry date of the contract.

M. Sub-contracting

Sub-contracting is the use of a commercial contract to 'get the work done'. It can provide ready trained staff and expertise for a limited period. Sub-contracted workers range from permanent employees of large organisations- such as building, computer or catering firms- to small one person businesses.

N. Zero hours contracts

The term 'zero hours' is generally understood to be an employment contract between an employer and a worker, where the employer is not obliged to provide the worker with any minimum hours of work, and the worker is not obliged to accept any hours of work that are offered to them.

Zero hours' contracts can be used to provide a flexible workforce to meet a temporary or changeable need for staff. Zero-hours contracts may suit some people who want occasional earnings and are able to be entirely flexible about when they work. However, the unpredictable nature of working times means that this arrangement won't suit others.

In many cases, an employer may find it more effective or appropriate to make use of agency workers, or recruit staff on fixed-term contracts - or it may turn out that the need is permanent and therefore a permanent member of staff should be recruited.

O. Home working

Home working can be when an employee regularly carries out all, or part of, their duties from home rather than the employer's premises. It could also be the occasional agreed day or it could be a full time arrangement. Advances in technology make it far simpler

to keep in touch and work away from the employer's premises. It does require a working relationship that is based upon trust and encourages employees to manage their own work.

P. Mobile working

Mobile working is where an employee works all or part of their working week at a location away from their employer's work place. Traditional mobile workers include sales representatives and delivery drivers. Employees will usually receive instructions by phone or computer at home or in their vehicle.

Q. Hot-desking

Hot-desking is where employees are not assigned their own desk but when they are in the office can use any desk or an available desk within a designated area. There is a growing trend for hot-desking where staff spend time working away from their office base and therefore share desks with colleagues who are also often away from the office.

R. Developing a policy that gets the best out of flexible working opportunities

Employers should consider introducing a flexible working policy. A policy can help to ensure consistency in how flexible working is discussed and handled. In advance of introducing a policy an employer should consider what they and their employees want out of the policy.

Acas has developed a sample flexible working policy that an employer can adapt to their needs which can be found at www.acas.org.uk/templates

III. HOW MIGHT AN EMPLOYER DEVELOP A FLEXIBLE WORKING POLICY?

An employer should base its policies on the needs of the organization, its customers and its employees.

In advance of creating a policy an employer should give serious consideration to what the main motivation behind its creation is, such as:

- Improved production levels
- Better work-life balance for employees
- Better customer care
- More committed employees

Any existing consultation and/or negotiating arrangements should be followed so that employees or their representatives can contribute to their views on any proposals. This is advantageous to an employer because employees will often be aware of the practical and potential problems of introducing new forms of flexible working.

A policy should include, for example:

- A statement that actively encourages employees to consider flexible working arrangements, provided that both the organization's and the employees objectives are met
- Be clear that the organization is committed to ensuring that individuals who request flexible working arrangements are not treated less favourably than their colleagues
- Details of the various flexible working options available
- How employees can request a flexible working arrangement
- Where to find further information

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